

NEUROSCIENCE AND MATHEMATICAL LEARNING

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Abstract: This article aims to present theoretical approaches between neuroscience and mathematical learning. It is a bibliographical study, in which we weave theoretical discussions about motivation and the opportune time for student learning, according to their cognitive development. The choice of the subject in question was motivated by the desire to help teachers and students to have a pleasant experience in teaching the aforementioned science (mathematics) by demystifying it as a discipline that is difficult to understand, complex, and as the main cause of school failure . Historically, many students have not been able to assimilate the content of mathematics and feel “incompetent” to absorb the subject, precisely because of this, its importance is defended, as an elementary science in all human existence; even the uneducated individual makes use of elements appropriate to mathematics in his daily life. We therefore believe, based on the theoretical references studied, in the dialogue between neurosciences and mathematics, to provide the improvement of teaching and learning.

Keywords: Mathematics, Neurosciences, Cognitive development, Teaching, Learning.

1. INTRODUCTION

The present work aims to present the importance of teaching mathematics embodied in the knowledge of neuroscience for this learning process, taking for granted that the teaching-learning phenomenon permeates approaches that involve an interdisciplinary perspective.

The choice of the theme in question was motivated because we understand that interdisciplinary studies of neuroscience with other disciplines are very recent, a few decades old, but that it is of paramount importance to help teachers and students to have a pleasant experience in teaching-learning of the mentioned science (Mathematics) demystifying it as a teaching discipline that is not very understandable, and even somewhat complex, whose code name received for decades is “villain” of school repetitions and failures.

In view of this, we aim to contribute to fundamental classes, through a study aimed at rescuing the ludic and fun mathematics class, so that the student has an instigating experience, full of meaning in his own daily life and a pleasant learning in the discipline, which many times it only occurs until the period of kindergarten and afterwards, such ludicity ends up being lost, as the content of the discipline becomes more complex.

It appears that Mathematics is part of everyone's daily life, but often this happens unnoticed. We use mathematics for a variety of situations, whether to have knowledge of an undefined area, for a sample of a certain research, which is something complex; either for a comparison of averages in analysis of variance as a statistical resource, or simply to measure the mass of a product/food using a scale.

For this reason, we present reflections in this work, based on neuroscience so that the teacher can appropriate and use it in his math class, thus making it more attractive and his teaching method more efficient; while the student is also provided with an instigating experience, encouraging their self-confidence, autonomy, and the search for more knowledge on the subject taught in the classroom, and consequently the effort employed for their learning is more rewarding.

We know that this is an arduous task, as the individuality of each student is known, the idiosyncratic factors that interfere in the learning process, the emergence of diagnoses, for example, of specific learning disorders ³; in addition to the different types of trauma and emotional burdens that produce a certain blockage in the student.

In these cases, we take into account the student's need to obtain help to overcome such difficulties, and for that, it is necessary to identify the problem/cause, the strengths and weaknesses and from there, it is expected that teachers and other educators can work together to establish strategies that will help the student to learn mathematics more effectively, thus reducing the negative consequences and providing a lighter and more satisfying learning experience.

³Research finds that 10 out of 100 people worldwide have a specific learning disorder.

For that, we use the bibliographical methodology as a guide for the work because we have in the literature an apparatus of effective methodologies that discuss the subject, where we gather in a clear and objective way, the purpose of making the learning of mathematics a possibility within everyone's reach; scenario in which the teacher and the student take turns in the role of protagonists and supporting actors, while at the same time they help each other, and are determined to take a journey together.

In this way, aiming to contribute to the teaching-learning of excellence in the mathematics class, we have divided the article into 4 sections. The first section has this introduction. These are preliminary explanations about the subject, choice of theme, motivations and objectives of the article; in the second section, we reveal brief considerations on cognitive neuroscientific development, its implications on educational processes, on learning in general; in the third section we present reflections on the Teaching-Learning of Mathematics relating them to Neuroscience and, in the last section, we conclude the subject in question.

2 COGNITIVE NEUROSCIENTIFIC DEVELOPMENT

Cognitive neuroscience is an interdisciplinary field, involving knowledge of genetics, biophysics, computational neuroscience, among others – which investigates potential neural substrates for mental processes. Within this approach, research on numerical cognition is developed, that is, the cognitive and neural bases of numbers and mathematics. A minimum knowledge of Mathematics is very relevant in anyone's daily life, but for many Mathematics is seen as a difficult subject to understand. This is due to a series of factors and one of them is contact with mathematics through outdated and rather boring methods, causing a cognitive block for learning mathematics.

There is extensive evidence that numerical skills in the early years of life are predictive of mathematical learning in the school years, and it is also in these early years that blockage and trauma to learning can occur.

In this case, many children and adolescents, despite having good neural health, as we know that neurological/cognitive problems, specific learning disorders, such as: dyscalculia, interfere with mathematics learning, are associated with the inability to learn mathematics as a personal limitation, however part of this lack of understanding of mathematics was or is due to poor teaching and cultural-educational systems.

It appears that for some students, for example, for those with dyscalculia, mathematics is very challenging. In this case, the student has difficulty understanding the quantity of things and therefore has difficulty understanding numbers and what they represent; difficulty in learning the tables (addition, subtraction, multiplication and division); to solve mathematical problems; to organize things logically and to measure. As adults, other difficulties are observed, such as estimating costs when shopping; has less ability in financial management; impairment in memorizing mathematical functions, in following a schedule, in performing mental calculations without the aid of a calculator, pencil and paper, difficulty estimating accurately and quickly or judging distances, among others.

Figure 1 – Division of the human brain.

Source: <https://mundoeducacao.uol.com.br/biologia/cerebro.htm>. Accessed on: January 11, 2022.

In figure 1 we see the human brain. It is related to memory, intelligence and emotions and is divided into two hemispheres, the left and the right. The hemispheres are divided into four cerebral lobes. Below we describe each of the divisions of the cerebral hemispheres.

- Frontal lobe (yellow): This is the part responsible for executive functions, which, according to Malloy-Diniz *et. al* (2008), where all processes that require planning, organization, sequences, decision, analysis, synthesis, executive attention (selective and sustained), coordination of strategies (election of priorities and secondary actions), behavioral inhibition, working memory take place , requirements of interests, perception of errors and construction of corrections.
- Temporal lobe (red): the region is responsible for the auditory perception of sounds and the different structures of phonological language, being the center of all language in our brain;

- Parietal lobe (blue): this part is connected to general sensitivity (tactile, proprioception, pain, etc.), spatial coordination, sensory-perceptual integration and attentional orientation;
- Occipital lobe (green): The occipital region is linked to all visual ability being the center of visual perceptions for everyday tasks.

According to Augusto Buchweitz (2016), in his article entitled “*Language and reading development in the brain today: neuromarkers and the case for prediction*”, the components of the language circuit are associated with levels of auditory processes; Key centers and processes include:

- (1) the primary auditory cortex, which processes raw auditory information;
- (2) the temporal-posterior and inferior parietal cortices, which process the systematic organization of word sounds;
- (3) the medial temporal cortex, associated with the meaning of words, and
- (4) the inferior frontal cortex, which processes the structure of language.

Neuroscience studies indicate that brain connections happen all the time and start in the 4th period of gestation. The brain has specific parts for a certain type of learning and its development also happens gradually. For example, the region of the brain called the temporoparietal, is part of the process of learning to read and is associated with the medial temporal cortex, this area does the work of linking sounds to letters (phonemes) and how they correspond. Between 5 and 8 years of age, a change in the volume of this brain region occurs in children, and the lack of volume increase interferes with the learning of word formation.

However, with regard to mathematics, it appears that when we reason about some issue that involves it, different areas of the brain are activated, including the frontal networks, the medial temporal lobe and, above all, the hippocampus, are mobilized.

The researcher dr. Analía Arévalo (2021), one of the coordinators of the Specialization course in Neurosciences at the HCFMUSP School of Permanent Education, clarifies that “Neuroscience is very vast and ranges from the behavioral area and motor rehabilitation, to

advanced cognition". So, in this way we see the importance of good brain development for healthy learning, whether in education or in other sectors of life.

3. THE TEACHING AND LEARNING OF MATHEMATICS AND NEUROSCIENCES

As we discussed above, mathematics is an elementary science in all human existence, even the non-schooled individual, makes use of elements appropriate to mathematics in their daily lives, whether it is a situation with numerical presentation, a question or problem of complex calculation, or in the simple everyday reasoning such as paying for a bus ticket, making a purchase, receiving change, etc.

It is known that, historically, many students have not been able to assimilate the content of mathematics, that they feel "incompetent" to absorb the subject, and some are forced to pass the grade/year, as if they had passed, so that goals established by the unit school, are reached. However, although the student has been 'approved', he continues without learning the necessary content and that may even be a prerequisite for other more complete subjects.

With regard to children, in the contemporary world, it is assured that from an early age, mathematics can be gradually introduced into their learning and behavioral repertoire, as they assimilate some content. It is said that the presentation of that science is carried out gradually, because the stage of child development is taken into account, that is, the information should not be like a flood of content, nor of a very complex nature, on the contrary, it should be passed on to the child, according to the compatibility of their maturation, their intellectual development, even observing the principles of neuroscience. On the other hand, there is clear evidence that the brain is plastic enough to justify ongoing and systematic instruction and intervention efforts for students who face persistent difficulties in learning mathematics.

With regard to teaching, Cosenza & Guerra (2011), ensure that educators can benefit from neuroscientific knowledge, planning their pedagogical practices in the development of activities that strengthen neuronal circuits, allowing the exploration of their potential in a creative and autonomous way. It is at this moment that scientific knowledge, combined with education, interferes in a positive and effective way in the teaching and learning processes.

For Brousseau (2008), the adaptation of students to different situations allows verifying that learning adequacy is inherent to human beings, that is, the same teaching, although unique, arrives differently for each individual. Therefore, it is extremely important that activities in the classroom are well planned and that most of them seek to be carried out in groups, so that the

student can verify the different points of view and ways that the resolution of a certain activity can have.

The task of dealing with numbers requires a capacity for abstraction, requires resourcefulness, and making this abstraction occur is not such an easy role. According to Dieudonné (1968):

[...] Mathematics has shared with Metaphysics the character of being a field of abstractions, far from reality and concrete experiences, which makes many people “obstinately rebellious to all abstract thinking, which is why they retreat before the slightest mathematical reasoning” . (DIEUDONNÉ, 1968, p. 42).

Nogueira (2017), literally translates the ideas of Piaget *et al.* (1968), where the teacher needs to be aware that the emotional and psychological side of the learner must be observed even before the teaching is received, that is, it is to analyze the psychological characteristics of each stage of learning of the human being:

[...] We need to know the student and have an idea of what we do to teach him before approaching the technical refinements. For this reason, the psychological chapter is the first and the pedagogical one is the last. Between the way and the possibility of doing, conditioned by the teacher and the student, there is matter, which is the substance of the dialogue. (Piaget *et al.* (1968) *apud* Nogueira (2017).

In this sense, we defend the teaching-learning process as a dynamic process, of relationship, of interaction between teacher and student, in constant communication that is capable of facing difficulties. In this interaction, it appears that we cannot fail to take into account the emotional state, the culture, the community, all these elements have implications for the behavior of children and adolescents, and contribute positively or negatively to learning, since the The problem of Mathematics is also cultural. It can even be noted how insufficient the incentive given by Brazilian families in general, to children and adolescents is still insufficient, even with regard to financial education, the economy and other subjects and situations involving mathematics, subjects that will accompany you for his entire adult life.

4. CONCLUSION

Thus, in this work, we reflect on the importance of teaching and learning mathematics with the support of neuroscience. We emphasized ideas and content with the aim of encouraging

teachers in their teaching practice with students who have mathematical learning difficulties, as well as in their mission to unwind the imbroglio *that* mathematics teaching has been suffering for decades; on the other hand, with this we encourage the rescue of the most attractive mathematics class, where the student has an instigating experience, is encouraged in his autonomy to seek more knowledge about the subject taught in the classroom, and its applicability in everyday life .

We understand that when it comes to teaching, there is not a single form, nor a single model of education to be followed, however, will, commitment, knowledge of the discipline and empathy are preponderant factors in an educational formation, be it for children, teenagers or adults. Finally, to fill in the various gaps in the teaching-learning process, we understand that educational practice can be much more successful when its hands are linked to neuroscience.

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